
DIFFERENCE IN TIME PERIOD WHILE SIMPLE HARMONIC MOTION AT DIFFERENT PLANETS – vertical motion of elastic string.

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Abstract

In this paper we studied about effect of gravitation on Simple harmonic motion at different planets. Simple harmonic motion (SHM) is a fundamental concept in physics and mechanics that explains the motion of a system that oscillates back and forth with a constant period around an equilibrium point. SHM is also can produce in an elastic string when we tied an end of string to a fixed point and hang a mass in other hand it can produced an harmonic motion. This motion is directly proportional to some factors like Mass of object, modulus of string and Gravity. In this work, we will change the gravitation acceleration as per different planets and observe the effect of this on SHM.

Introduction

SHM is a sort of periodic motion that happens when a system is displaced from its equilibrium position and encounters a restoring acceleration that is proportional to the displacement and acts in the opposite direction. A spring or an elastic medium normally provides the restoring acceleration, and the motion has a constant period, amplitude, and frequency. The amplitude, period, and frequency of the oscillations are critical characteristics that may be calculated using the initial conditions and system features. SHM offers a wide range of applications in industries such as engineering, astronomy, and music. Understanding SHM principles is essential for analysing and forecasting the behaviour of many physical systems.

When we talk about SHM in string there are two types of motion in string (a) Horizontal motion of elastic string and (b) Vertical motion of elastic strings. In both strings hook's law is applicable.

When an elastic string is stretched or squeezed and then released, Simple Harmonic Motion (SHM) can occur. The string then vibrates back and forth around its equilibrium position.

The displacement of the string from its equilibrium position can be used to characterise its velocity, as shown by the equation.

$$Y(t) = A \sin(\omega t + \phi)$$

Where y is the displacement of the string from its equilibrium position, A is the oscillation's amplitude (i.e., the maximum displacement from equilibrium), ω is the oscillation's angular frequency (i.e., the rate at which the string oscillates back and forth), t is time, and ϕ is the oscillation's phase angle (i.e., the initial displacement of the string at time $t = 0$).

Explanation

Vertical motion of elastic strings:-

The restoring acceleration in Simple Harmonic Motion (SHM) is directly proportional to the displacement from the equilibrium position and acts in the opposite direction of the displacement.

When an object is conducting SHM in vertical motion, it is usually subject to two accelerations: gravity and elasticity. The object's elasticity is defined by its Young's modulus, which describes the stiffness of the material it is made of.

Young's modulus, also known as modulus of elasticity, is a measurement of how much a material will deform (stretch or compress) in response to an applied acceleration. It is defined as the stress-to-strain ratio, where stress is the acceleration per unit area applied to the material and strain is the proportionate change in material length.

In the instance of SHM in vertical motion, the item is initially displaced from its equilibrium position and receives a restoring acceleration proportionate to that displacement. This restoring acceleration is provided by the object's elasticity, which is defined by its Young's modulus. Because of its shifting position relative to the Earth, the object receives a changing gravitational pull as it oscillates up and down. The gravitational pull, however, is generally constant and may be ignored as long as the amplitude of the oscillation is minimal. As a result, in SHM, the motion of the item in vertical motion is mostly dictated by the restoring acceleration produced by the object's elasticity, which is characterised by its Young's modulus.

Consider an object of mass ' m ' suspended from a spring with a spring constant ' k ' and a length ' L ' as shown below:

Assuming the object is initially at rest and is displaced downwards by a small distance 'x' from its equilibrium position, the gravitational acceleration acting on the object is given by 'mg' (where 'g' is the acceleration due to gravity), and the restoring acceleration provided by the spring is given by Hooke's law as 'kx' .

The net acceleration acting on the object is given by:

$$F_{\text{net}} = mg - kx$$

Using Newton's second law, we can write:

$$ma = mg - kx$$

where 'a' is the acceleration of the object.

Rearranging the above equation, we get:

$$a = g - (k/m)x$$

We can rewrite this equation in terms of angular frequency, ω , which is related to the period of oscillation T by $T = 2\pi/\omega$. The angular frequency is given by:

$$\omega = \sqrt{k/m}$$

Substituting this into the above equation, we get:

$$a = -\omega^2 x + g$$

We can rewrite this equation to find x:

$$x = (g/\omega^2) (1 - \cos(\omega t))$$

This equation expresses the object's position as a function of time in terms of gravitational acceleration 'g' and angular frequency.

The period of oscillation T can alternatively be expressed in terms of gravitational acceleration and spring length:

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{m/k} = 2\pi \sqrt{L/g}$$

This equation demonstrates that the period of oscillation is determined solely by the length of the spring and the gravitational acceleration, and is unaffected by the object's mass or the spring constant.

$T = 2\pi \sqrt{m/k} = 2\pi \sqrt{L/g}$ is the relation of time period of a 'm' mass object to complete one SHM and gravitational acceleration.

Now we check what variation are come from changing gravity.

At moon

From equation $T = 2\pi \sqrt{L/g}$ it's clear that time period of an vertical string is depends on length of string and gravitational acceleration. The Moon has a gravitational acceleration of approximately 1.62 m/s^2 (meters per second squared). This is about 16.6% of the gravitational acceleration on Earth, which are approximately 9.81 m/s^2 . So, an object that weighs 100 kilograms on Earth would weigh only about 16.6 kilograms on the Moon due to the difference in gravitational acceleration. This is approximat $1\sqrt{6}$ to the gravitation of earth.

We can write it like this

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{L/g} \text{ -----(1)}$$

Here value of 2π and L is constant so we can say

$$T \propto 1/\sqrt{g}$$

Replace g by $g/6$

$$T \propto \sqrt{6/g}$$

So by this relation we can say that on moon value of gravitational acceleration will decrease and due to its inverse relation with time period, the time period of a simple harmonic motion will be longer on the Moon compared to the time period on Earth. This means that the oscillations will be slower on the Moon, taking more time to complete one cycle.

At mars

From equation $T = 2\pi \sqrt{L/g}$ it's clear that time period of an vertical string is depends on length of string and gravitational acceleration. Mars has a gravitational acceleration of approximately 3.921 m/s^2 (meters per second squared). This is about 40 % (approx.) of the gravitational acceleration on Earth, which is approximately 9.81 m/s^2 . So, an object that weighs 100 kilograms on Earth would weigh only about 40 kilograms (approx.) on Mars due to the difference in gravitational acceleration. This is approximat $2/5$ to the gravitation of earth.

We can write it like this

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{L/g} \text{ -----(1)}$$

Here value of 2π and L is constant so we can say

$$T \propto 1/\sqrt{g}$$

Replace g by $g/5$

$$T \propto \sqrt{5/2g}$$

So by this relation we can say that on Mars value of gravitational acceleration will decrease and due to its inverse relation with time period, the time period of a simple harmonic motion will be longer on the Mars compared to the time period on Earth but short than moon. This means that the oscillations will be slower on the Mars, taking more time to complete one cycle.

At Mercury

Mercury has a gravitational acceleration of approximately 3.7 m/s^2 (meters per second squared) at its surface. This is about 39.66 % (approx. to 40%) of the gravitational acceleration on Earth, which is approximately 9.81 m/s^2 . So, an object that weighs 100 kilograms on Earth would weigh only about 40 kilograms on Mercury due to the difference in gravitational acceleration. The gravitational acceleration at Mercury is same as Mars.

So the results are also same as mars

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{L/g} \text{ -----(1)}$$

Here value of 2π and L is constant so we can say

$$T \propto 1/\sqrt{g}$$

Replace g by $g/5$

$$T \propto \sqrt{5/2g}$$

So by this relation we can say that on Mercury value of gravitational acceleration is equal to Mars and due to its inverse relation with time period, the time period of a simple harmonic motion will be longer on the Mercury compared to the time period on Earth but short than moon. This means that the oscillations will be slower on the Mars, taking more time to complete one cycle.

At Venus

Venus has a gravitational acceleration of approximately 8.87 m/s^2 (meters per second squared) at its surface. This is about 90.7% of the gravitational acceleration on Earth, which is approximately 9.81 m/s^2 . So, an object that weighs 100 kilograms on Earth would weigh about 91 kilograms on Venus due to the difference in gravitational acceleration. The difference between gravitational acceleration of Earth and Venus is not much it have a little difference of 1.06 m/s^2 approximant 10% less than Earth.

So the result is

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{L/g} \text{ -----(1)}$$

Here value of 2π and L is constant so we can say

$$T \propto 1/g$$

Replace g by $g/10$

$$T \propto 10/9g$$

So the difference between Earth's and Venus's gravitation is less and the time period of a simple harmonic motion on Venus is almost equal to earth it has a small difference of 10% that's why a cycle of SHM is taking a little more time at Venus with comparison to earth.

At Jupiter

Jupiter has a gravitational acceleration of approximately 24.79 m/s^2 (meters per second squared) at its cloud tops. This is about 2.53 times the gravitational acceleration on Earth, which are approximately 9.81 m/s^2 . So, an object that weighs 100 kilograms on Earth would weigh about 253 kilograms on Jupiter due to the difference in gravitational acceleration.

So the result is

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{L/g} \text{ -----(1)}$$

Here value of 2π and L is constant so we can say

$$T \propto 1/g$$

Replace g by $g \cdot 2.53$

$T \propto 1/2.53g$

Because Jupiter's gravity acceleration is approximately 2.53 times that of Earth, the time period of a SHM will be shorter on Jupiter than on Earth. This means that the oscillations on Jupiter will be faster, taking less time to complete one cycle.

Furthermore, Jupiter's powerful magnetic field and intense radiation can have an impact on the behaviour of oscillating systems and electromagnetic devices. This can result in oscillation amplitude and frequency variations, as well as interference with electronic devices.

At Saturn

Saturn has a gravitational acceleration of roughly 10.44 m/s² (meters per second squared). This is approximately 1.065 times the gravitational acceleration on Earth, which are 9.81 m/s². As a result of the difference in gravitational acceleration, an object weighing 100 kilogrammes on Earth would weigh approximately 106.5 kilogrammes on Saturn.

Saturn, like Jupiter, is a gas giant planet with varying gravity based on altitude and position inside its atmosphere.

So the result is

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{L/g} \text{ -----(1)}$$

Here value of 2π and L is constant so we can say

$$T \propto 1/g$$

Replace g by $g \cdot 1.065$

$T \propto 1/1.065g$

Because Saturn's gravity acceleration is approximately 1.065 times that of Earth, the time period of a SHM will be slightly shorter on Saturn than on Earth. This means that the oscillations on Saturn will be slightly faster, and one cycle will take slightly less time to complete.

The difference in time period caused by gravity is, however, relatively modest, and other factors such as the effective length of the pendulum and the amplitude of oscillation can have a larger impact on the time period of SHM.

At Uranus

Uranus has a gravitational acceleration of roughly 8.69 m/s² (metres per second squared). This is roughly 0.886 times the gravitational acceleration on Earth, which is 9.81 m/s². As a result of the difference in gravitational acceleration, an object weighing 100 kilogrammes on Earth would weigh approximately 88.6 kilogrammes on Uranus.

$$T = 2\pi \sqrt{L/g} \text{ -----(1)}$$

Here value of 2π and L is constant so we can say

$$T \propto 1/\sqrt{g}$$

Replace g by $g \cdot 0.886$

$$T \propto 1/\sqrt{0.886g}$$

Because the acceleration due to gravity on Uranus is approximately 0.886 times that of Earth, the time period of an SHM on Uranus will be slightly longer than on Earth. This indicates that the oscillations on Uranus will be slightly slower, taking slightly longer to complete.

It is crucial to remember, however, that Uranus is a gas giant planet with a complex atmosphere and magnetic field that can impact the behaviour of an oscillating system in ways other than the difference in gravitational acceleration.

Conclusion

It has shown that the simple analysis of the SHM at different planets (or in different gravity's). The method and calculation is accurate or the values are almost in approximation. This work shows a brief effect on the time period in SHM on different planets. The basic principle of SHM is following the hook's law and in SHM (linear string) time period is depend on length of string and gravitational acceleration. SHM use in our daily life for example: - pendulum clock, spring, musical instruments and electric circuit etc.

Reference

[1] Using simple harmonic motion to follow the Galilean moons—testing Kepler's third law on as mall system. I G de Moraes and J A M Pereira 2009.

[2] Study on Simple Harmonic Motion And its Application on spring. Abhishek Yernagula [1], Akshay Thorat [2], Arbaj Khan [3], Prof. Parmeshwari Aland [4] Professor, Ajeenkya DY Patil University 2019
